

Bioinformatics: A New Tool in Dentistry

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Abstract

Bioinformatics is a new speciality that focuses on using information science to solve biological problems. It deals with the collecting, storing, retrieving and analysing data from databases. Bioinformatics has supported and promoted the research in the field of healthcare and has taken it to next level. Bioinformatics can encourage the research in dentistry by understanding the underlying pathways and mechanisms in certain oral diseases. It can also help in early prediction and personalized treatment of cancer that may prove beneficial in early detection and accurate treatment of cancer. Bioinformatics supports in developing patient care databases, image analysis of X- rays, CT and MRI. Diagnostic abilities will also multiple with databases management. Salivonomics is sub-speciality of bioinformatics dealing with saliva knowledge base enabling global exploration of data relevant to saliva. Incorporation of bioinformatics with AI and machine learning can lead to immense positive outcomes in field of research in personalised medicine and gene therapy. This review will help to understand the tools used in bioinformatics and its role in dentistry.

Introduction

Computing in biology is boon in healthcare as it enhances our understanding and improve decision making ability. COVID 19 epidemic has taught us new ways to deal with biological virus. Consider a biological emergency in future, we are prepared to handle in better way. Laboratory scientists will isolate its genetic material - a molecule of nucleic acid consisting of a long polymer of four different types of residues - and determine the sequence. Computer programs will then take over. Screening this new genome against a data bank of all known genetic messages will characterize the virus and reveal its relationship with viruses previously studied. The analysis will help in developing antiviral therapies which work on protein that are building blocks of virus. A disruption of protein will hamper structure and function of virus [1].

Bioinformatics can be defined as an integrative field of mathematics, computer science, and biology to solve biological problems. It is an interdisciplinary field requiring in-depth understanding of biological systems, algorithms and statistics. Bioinformatics incorporates the concepts of machine learning, artificial intelligence

and neural networks to analyse biological data to provide useful results and conclusions [2].

Figure 1: Show the Different Management of Data in Modern Biology and Medicine

Human genome project was declared jointly by Prime Minister of the United Kingdom Tony Blair and President of the United States Bill Clinton on 26 June 2000. The human genome is fundamentally about information, and computers were essential both for the determination of the sequence and for the applications

More Information

How to cite this article: Saxena M, Srivastava S, Dular MS. Bioinformatics: A New Tool in Dentistry. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(1):83-90.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(1).12

Keywords:

bioinformatics,
healthcare,
personalised medicine,
dentistry.

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to biology and medicine that are already flowing from it. Computing contributed not only the raw capacity for processing and storage of data, but also the mathematically-sophisticated methods required to achieve the results. The marriage of biology and computer science has created a new field called bioinformatics. The central dogma of life is DNA, RNA and protein. The classic data of bioinformatics include DNA sequences of genes or full genomes; amino acid sequences of proteins; and three-dimensional structures of proteins, nucleic acids and protein–nucleic acid complexes. Additional “-omics” data streams include: transcriptomics, the pattern of RNA synthesis from DNA; proteomics, the distribution of proteins in cells; interactomics, the patterns of protein–protein and protein–nucleic acid interactions; and metabolomics, the nature and traffic patterns of transformations of small molecules by the biochemical pathways active in cells [1].

Tools and Techniques in Bioinformatics

Importance of Biological Databases

A biological database is a computerized software or website designed to update, query, and retrieve

information. The huge amounts of data generated are stored in online databases. Databases can be categorised as Primary and secondary databases. Primary databases include experimental data like nucleotide sequence, protein sequence or macromolecular structure. E.g.: Protein Databank. Secondary databases include results derived from primary data. E.g.: Ensemble [2].

Database Storage and Retrieval of Data

In bioinformatics, data banks are used to store and organize data. Many of these entities collect DNA and RNA sequences from scientific papers and genome projects. The European Molecular Biology Laboratory Nucleotide Sequence Database (EMBL-Bank) in the United Kingdom, the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ), and GenBank of the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) in the United States oversees the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) which acts to facilitate exchange of data on a daily basis [1].

A number of databases have similarly been established for protein information [3].

Table 1: Different Types of Databases and Their Websites

Data base	Function	website
Protein Information Resource (PIR)	Protein information	(http://pir.georgetown.edu/),
Protein Data Bank (PDB)	Protein	(http://www.pdb.org/),
Nucleic Acid Data Base (NADB)	Nucleic acid	(http://ndbserver.rutgers.edu/)
Molecular Modeling Data Base (MMDB)	3 D macromolecular structure.	(http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Structure/MMDB/mmdb.shtml).
Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG)	Metabolimic pathway	(http://www.genome.jp/kegg/),
Database of Interacting Proteins (DIP)	Protein	(http://dip.doe-mbi.ucla.edu/),
PubMed	Bibilographic	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PubMed/
Gene Expression Profiling Interactive Analysis(GEPIA)		
Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results (SEER)		

Sequence Alignment

DNA is the genetic material that acts as a medium to transmit genetic information from one generation to another. All the living things diverge over time from the common ancestor by evolution through changes in their DNA.

DNA defined the species and individuals, which makes the DNA sequence fundamental to the research on the structures and functions of cells and the decoding of life mysteries [4]. DNA sequencing technologies could help biologists and health care providers in a broad range of applications such as molecular cloning, breeding, finding pathogenic genes, and comparative and evolution studies. DNA sequencing technologies ideally should be fast, accurate, easy-to-operate, and cheap. In 1977, Frederick Sanger developed DNA sequencing

technology which was based on chain-termination method (also known as Sanger sequencing), and Walter Gilbert developed another sequencing technology based on chemical modification of DNA and subsequent cleavage at specific bases [5]. Hence, the ability to sequence the DNA of an organism is one of the most important and primary requirement in biological research. Sequence alignment (SA) is usually the first step performed in bioinformatics to understand the molecular phylogeny of an unknown sequence. This is done by aligning the unknown sequence with one or more known database sequences to predict the common portions as the residues perform functional and structural role tend to be preserved by natural selection in the course of evolution.

Sequence alignment is a method to identify homologous sequences. The sequences may be nucleotide sequences (DNAs or RNAs) or amino acid sequences (Proteins). The rearrangement process may introduce one or more spaces or gaps in the alignment. A gap indicates a possible loss or gain of a residue; thus, evolutionary insertion or deletion (indel), translocations and inversion events can be observed in SA.

This is done by aligning the unknown sequence with one or more known sequences to predict the common portions. Aligned sequences of nucleotide or amino acid residues are typically represented as rows within a matrix [6].

Alignment Types

Sequence alignment is the comparison of residues between sequences. There are two types of sequence

alignment, pairwise sequence alignment (PSA) and multiple sequence alignment (MSA). PSA considers two sequences at a time whereas MSA aligns more than two related sequences. MSA is more beneficial than PSA as it considers multiple members of a sequence family and thus provides more biological information. Proteins are key biological molecules that carry structural and functional information therefore sequence alignment at amino acid level is more relevant [2].

Alignment methods

Global alignment is performed on sequences with similar length and alignment has to be accomplished throughout the length. Local alignment is done to know the local similar regions among the sequences. When there is a large difference in the lengths of the sequences to be compared, local alignment is generally performed. Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sequence Alignment of Mammalian Histone Protein

A sequence alignment, produced by ClustalO, of mammalian histone proteins.

Sequences are the amino acids for residues 120-180 of the proteins. Residues that are conserved across all sequences are highlighted in grey. Below the protein sequences is a key denoting conserved sequence (*), conservative mutations (:), semi-conservative mutations (.), and non-conservative mutations ().

Interpretation

If two sequences in an alignment share a common ancestor, mismatches can be interpreted as point mutations and gaps as indels (that is, insertion or deletion mutations) introduced in one or both lineages in the time since they diverged from one another. In sequence alignments of proteins, the degree of similarity between amino acids occupying a particular position in the sequence can be interpreted as a rough measure of how conserved a particular region or sequence motif is among lineages.

The **FASTA format** is a text-based format for representing either nucleotide sequences or amino acid (protein) sequences, in which nucleotides or amino

acids are represented using single-letter codes and compares with existing data base.

Clustal Omega is a multiple sequence alignment program for aligning three or more sequences together in a computationally efficient and accurate manner. It produces biologically meaningful multiple sequence alignments of divergent sequences [7].

Tools for Database Searching for Similar Sequences

Searching a sequence database for sequences that are similar to the query sequence is the most common type of database similarity search. The first rapid search method was FASTA, which found short common patterns in the query and database sequences and joined these into an alignment. The Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) is similar to FASTA but is gaining popularity because of its ability to search rarer and more significant sequences. PAM250 Scoring Matrix is a scoring matrix based on an evolutionary model that predicts the type of amino acid changes over a long period of time. PSI-BLAST and PHI-BLAST are iterative search methods that improve on the detection rate of BLAST and FASTA. Pfam and Simple Modular Architecture Research Tool (SMART) are used for

protein domain family analysis. Phylogenetic analysis using parsimony (PAUP) and phylogenetic inference package (PHYIP) are software packages available for the phylogenetic analysis of macromolecular sequences.

The program RasMol is the best-known viewer for macromolecular structures [10].

Figure 3- Different types of Phylogenetic tree.

- A) An example of a cladogram representation: a branching diagram assumed to be an estimate of a phylogeny.
- B) An example of a phylogram. A phylogram is different from a cladogram with respect to the fact that the branch lengths are proportional to the amount of inferred evolutionary change.
- C) An example of an unrooted cladogram. An unrooted tree can be rooted on any of its branches, and so there are many rooted trees that can be derived from a single unrooted tree.
- D) An example of a circular cladogram. These kinds of layout types place the nodes in concentric rings around the center.
- E) An example of a slanted cladogram. The sloped version of the rectangular layout remains equally informative and efficient.
- F) An example of a hyperbolic tree.
- G) 3D Trees by 3DPE (3D Phylogeny Explorer) tool.
- H) 3D tree visualized by Arena3D visualization tool.

Phylogenetic Analysis

Phylogenetics is useful in understanding the way species have evolved along with the differences and similarities with their predecessors. Phylogenetics unveils the origin and spread of the human

immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and the origin and subsequent evolution of the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and COVID-19 viruses. This in turn guides us to develop appropriate vaccine. Initially, the parameter for assessing the similarities and variation

among species were the morphological traits but now deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), ribonucleic acid (RNA) and protein sequence has replaced it in phylogenetics [8].

A phylogenetic tree, also known as a phylogeny, is a diagram that depicts the lines of evolutionary descent of different species, organisms, or genes from a common ancestor. It may be rooted or unrooted, bifurcating or multi furcating, circular or rectangular as depicted in Figure 3. A clade is a piece of a phylogeny that includes an ancestral lineage and all the descendants of that ancestor. [9] A phylogenetic tree is formed as an outcome of sequence analysis performed on the DNA or RNA strings. Various string processing algorithms are available which can quickly analyse these DNA and RNA sequences and build a phylogeny of sequences or species based on their similarity and dissimilarity. A comparison of given set of sequence with the sequence stored in database will provide accurate information. This requires the comparison of multiple sequence by dynamic programming. Sequence comparison reveals the patterns of shared history between species, helping in the prediction of ancestral states.

A phylogenetic tree shows relationships and provides a visual representation of the estimated branching order of the taxonomical groups. It can be used to determine relationships among a collection of viruses, bacteria, animal or species, or other operational taxonomic units. They are also important in identifying viral subtype and new recombinant subtypes arising from combinations of known subtypes. Factors such as population subdivision, migration, and changing population size impact the tree. Forces such as recombination, mutation, and selection impact the genetic data of a given tree [2].

Protein Structure and Function Prediction

Protein structure prediction is the inference of the three-dimensional structure of a protein from its amino acid sequence—that is, the prediction of its secondary and tertiary structure from primary structure. Protein prediction is essential in designing of drug and vaccines. The initial step in protein structure prediction is to confirm if a protein sequence or part of a protein sequence has any similarities with sequences of known structures present in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) [10]. The Protein Data Bank is the single worldwide archive of primary structural data of biological macromolecules. Many secondary sources of information are derived from PDB data [11].

Structure prediction is often divided into three areas: ab initio prediction, fold recognition, and homology modeling. The distinction between these areas is usually based on the extent to which information in sequence and structural databases is used in the construction of a model. Ab initio prediction is to

predict the structure of a protein based entirely on the laws of physics and chemistry in its purest form and does not rely on information in databases. The term ab initio or de novo is also applied to the prediction of the structure of proteins for which there is no similar structure in the Protein Database (PDB) but where local sequence and structural relationships involving short protein fragments, as well as secondary structure prediction, are incorporated into the prediction process. Fold recognition, often referred to as “threading,” corresponds to the case where one or more structures (templates) similar to a given target sequence exist in the PDB but are not easily identified. Here the main challenge is to find the best set of templates, but, in general, it will be difficult to build an accurate model. At the current stage of the technology, the most accurate models are obtained when a single template can be found in the PDB that has a high level of sequence similarity to the target protein. The process of building a model from such a template is referred to as homology or comparative modeling. [12]

Internet Computing Systems for Protein Structure Prediction

Access to a computing system designed for bioinformatics analysis is required. For example, a user account on a computer system running a Unix-flavored operating system (e.g., Solaris, Linux, or IRIX), sufficient memory, disk space, and applications (including an editor, a multiple sequence alignment program, a sequence similarity search program, and access to up-to-date biological sequence, structure, and bibliographic databanks) are required. Such facilities are available to registered users of the UK Human Genome Mapping Project Resource Centre (HGMP-RC) [10].

Metabolic Pathway

A metabolic pathway is a network of related chemical reactions catalyzed by enzymes that collaboratively produce or degrade one or a few metabolites. Reconstruction of metabolic networks (pathways) plays an important role in studying biological systems. Together with other types of biological networks, metabolic pathways can help interpret relationships between genotype and phenotype, and clarify essential mechanisms underlying cellular physiology. Most known metabolic pathways stored in the pathway databases such as the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG). The high-quality manual annotations of metabolic pathways are valuable resources for studying metabolisms, but they only account for a small portion of pathways in most organisms. Therefore, automatic computational reconstruction of metabolic pathways has been an important problem to solve in bioinformatics and computational biology.

The most common approach for metabolic pathway construction is based on mapping a group of gene and

protein sequences of an organism to known reference pathways according to sequence homology. The matched reference metabolic pathways serve as templates to position the genes and proteins (e.g. enzymes) in order to construct the metabolic pathways that they participate in [13].

Integration of Bioinformatics in Dentistry

Detection of Oral Cancer

Cancer is one of the leading causes of mortality around the world accounting for about 10 million deaths in 2020 according to the World Health Organization [14]. Unfortunately, more than 50% of patients with oral cancer display evidence of spread to regional lymph nodes and metastases at the time of diagnosis, and approximately two-thirds of patients have apparent symptoms at presentation, a negative prognostic indicator.

Microarray Technology

Presently, microarray technology is widely used in cancer research, diagnosis, and tumor classification for more than a decade. Microarray technique is adopted due to limitations with conventional techniques of gene investigation in cancer which are mainly time-consuming and cost-ineffective. One of the earliest applications of microarray was to identify differences in gene expression between normal and cancer cells. DNA microarray analysis involves the use of an oligonucleotide chip, cDNA chip, and genomic chip. Oligonucleotide microarrays are used for studying gene expression, Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP), mutation, and genotyping analyses, and cDNA microarrays are usually used for gene expression analysis. The microarrays are broadly used to understand the genetic and epigenetic makeup of cancer cells. They are also used to decipher signal pathways of cancer-relevant transcription factors which have advanced the scientific understanding of how cancer-relevant transcription factors control gene networks and ultimately cancer development. Microarray technology also allows the cell's status to be investigated on the molecular scale and is very pivotal in future cancer diagnosis as traditional methods cannot distinguish between morphologically similar but molecularly different tumors. The molecular differences significantly affect the clinical course of a disease. Till now, microarrays are a major tool for the investigation of global gene expression for all aspects of human disease and biomedical research [1].

Applications of Microarrays in Oral Pathology

In the oral cavity, several conditions including oral cancer and pre-cancer have been found to have some genetic basis.

As of now, several precancerous conditions and lesions have been identified, though only a small fraction of these turn into malignancy. However, there is no single method by which the behaviour of these lesions can be

predicted. It is understood that genetic alterations take place much before morphologic changes in the oral cavity occur. Microarrays may be able to identify those genetic alterations that are more likely to determine the progression of a premalignant lesion to frank malignancy. One can also examine targets for drug discovery upon identifying the gene that plays a significant role in a particular disease. For example, if we compare normal cells to cancer cells and discover a gene that is turned on in that particular type of cancer, we may be able to target that gene in cancer therapy. Today, therapies that directly target malfunctioning genes are already in use and are showing exceptional results. Microarrays are used commonly to detect viruses and other pathogens from blood samples. More recently they have been used to identify inheritable markers, and therefore have been used as a genotyping tool [3].

Precancers and early-stage oral cancers cannot be adequately identified by visual inspection alone and may easily be overlooked and neglected, even by highly-trained professionals with broad experience. Thus, a method of detection at early, curable stages is crucial and may lead to a reduction in the currently unacceptably high oral cancer morbidity and mortality rates. Evolution of the OralCDx[®] system has significantly contributed to negating this drawback. A critical component of OralCDx[®] is the use of computer-assisted image analysis of the oral brush biopsy sample. The application of new, non-algorithmic, neural network computers that were developed in the late 1980s for missile defense. In recent years, neural networks have been successfully applied to several medical diagnostic procedures, including cervical smear screening and interpretation of digital radiologic images such as chest radiographs and mammograms. The OralCDx[®] neural network assists in the search for potentially abnormal cells in oral brush biopsy samples, which then are interpreted by the pathologist. The identification of these abnormal cells is labor intensive, fatiguing, and time consuming; more importantly, these abnormalities are also easily overlooked [15].

Patient Care Databases

Patient care databases are online storage including data related to the patient's diagnosis, procedures, drug prescription etc. Information on rare cases can be stored and can be easily accessed. Machine learning algorithms applied on the obtained data that can be used to give appropriate and effective treatment at minimal cost. A personalised well-designed hospital database can be used to collect up-to-date information from the visiting patient. This makes the relevant information available with a click-of-a-button. If a patient needs the services of healthcare providers in different hospitals, exchange of information is possible.

It is an important tool to monitor and improve healthcare services. It can also assist with documentation and billing. Reduction of paperwork and clerical staff can reduce the medical facility running costs. Health Database organization (HDOs) decided on two critical dimensions of databases: comprehensiveness and inclusiveness. Comprehensiveness describes the completeness of records of patient care events and information relevant to an individual patient. Inclusiveness refers to which populations in a geographic area are included in a database. The more inclusive a database, the more it approaches coverage of 100 percent of the population that its developers intend to include [16].

Image Analysis

Computational analysis of medical images, moreover, can allow the discovery of disease patterns and correlations among cohorts of patients with the same disease, thus suggesting common causes or providing useful information for better therapies and cures. Machine learning and deep learning applied to medical images, in particular, have produced new, unprecedented results that can pave the way to advanced frontiers of medical discoveries. To mention a few, these image modalities include X-ray radiography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), computed tomography (CT) scan, and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT). Since 2010s, new computational analyses of medical images have been made possible through machine learning.

It provides very accurate, time & efforts saving, and less expensive diagnosis which can be used in the medical imaging profession [17].

Salivaomics Knowledge Base

Saliva (oral fluid) is an emerging biofluid for non-invasive diagnostics used in the detection of human diseases. The need to advance saliva research is strongly emphasized by the National Institute of Dental and Craniofacial Research. (NIDCR) As a computational and informatics infrastructure that can permit global exploration and utilization, the Salivaomics Knowledge Base (SKB) is being created by aligning (1) the saliva biomarker discovery and validation resources at UCLA with (2) the ontology resources developed by the OBO (Open Biomedical Ontologies) Foundry [6], including the new Saliva Ontology (SALO) that is described in this communication. The Salivaomics Knowledge Base (SKB; [http:// www.skb.ucla.edu/](http://www.skb.ucla.edu/)) is a data repository, management system and web resource constructed to support human salivary proteomics, transcriptomics, miRNA, metabolomics and microbiome research. The SKB will provide the first web resource dedicated to salivary omics studies and will contain the data and information needed to explore the biology, diagnostic potentials, pharmacoproteomics and pharmacogenomics of human saliva. It has an effective information retrieval system and carefully designed data format and employs an open data model. Figure 1 shows the SKB's three-tier service oriented architecture with a Data Layer, Ontology Layer and Interface Layer [18].

Figure 4: The SKB Architecture

The SKB is based on a three-layer architecture. Data sources are stored in the data layer. In the ontology layer data elements from these data sources are mapped to nodes in controlled vocabularies. The interface layer allows query, browsing and submission. For instance, the interface layer receives user requests, submits queries to the data layer through the ontology layer and obtains corresponding results. The three layers connect data from consumers (users submitting query) with data providers (data sources) via ontologies.

Conclusion

Research in dental sciences can be metamorphosed by the evolution of high-throughput techniques and generation of large amount of data. The detailed study of the molecular sequences and structures can aid in understanding the genotypes and their clinical phenotypes. The future of dentistry with bioinformatics shows the analysis of clinical data based on genomic information that will increase our understanding of the underlying mechanisms. With this insight, we can eventually change the current practice of dentistry, including diagnostics, therapeutics, and prognostics of common oral diseases and disorders. This new approach to dental medicine will be known at molecular level that is missing in today's practice. Genomics and proteomics hold the promise to change then practice of dentistry their potential to identify risk factors and therapeutic targets in the field of oncology. Theoretical disciplines like bioinformatics and data mining will aid us greatly in understanding this complex picture. Saliva Ontology is an ongoing exploratory initiative. The ontology will be used to facilitate salivaomics data retrieval and integration across multiple fields of research together with data analysis and data mining. Current state of the art in both genomics and proteomics and the theoretical disciplines suggests that a proper combination of experimental and theoretical results, obtained with different methods, will soon become the gold standard for the study of oral diseases.

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